

A NOTE ON INORGANIC CHROMATOGRAPHIC ESTIMATIONS FROM THE DIMENSIONS OF THE ZONE

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Srikantan and Krishnan (this *Journal*, 1949, 28, 415) have used the chromatographic method of estimating copper in brass and bronze, and to measure the concentration from the dimensions of chromatograms have adopted Freundlich's adsorption isotherm. The data in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) illustrate for copper cation from $M/25$ to $M/200$ strengths of nitrate solutions. The length of the chromatogram being directly proportionate to concentration, h/c was constant giving a value of 181 (av.) with 1 c.c. of the copper nitrate solution in each case and the diameter of the tube being 0.7 cm. and for the same composition but different diameter of tube in the same quantity of solution r^2h was constant.

The results in this paper with different quantities of solutions are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Prepared alumina as before. 100-120 mesh. Strength of copper nitrate solution = $M/200$. Diameter of tube = 0.7 cm.

Quantity of solution.	Length of chromatogram.	Buffered to p_H 9.4
1 c.c.	0.4 cm.	0.3 cm.
2	1.1	0.6
3	2.6	1.0
4	3.1	—
5	3.7	—

It is seen from Table I, column 2 that the length of the chromatogram is not proportional to the quantity of the solution chromatographed. Thus, 5 c.c. of the solution of $M/200$ copper nitrate do not produce five times the length of the chromatogram of 1 c.c. of the same solution in the same tube. The length is more than five times. A similar observation has been made by us (unpublished) on the anionic chromatogram from phosphate solutions; while 1 c.c. of the phosphate solution gives 5 mm. of chromatogram (on alumina developed by ammonium molybdate) and 2 c.c. of the same solution give 12 mm. length.

It is perhaps most likely that as the solution to be chromatographed passes through the adsorbent, there is a change in the H-ion concentration at the surface of the adsorbent. Schawab *et al.* (*Naturwiss.*, 1934, 28, 44; *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1937, 50, 546, 691; 1938, 51, 709) recommend for cations a p_H of 9.4 and for anions a p_H of 5.3. Alterations of p_H might affect the adsorbability of the ions under consideration and different volumes of solution passing through p_H range, optimum for the adsorption of ions, changes making the adsorption partially reversible and thus the column tends to

increase in length more than proportionately. Such a view looks very plausible in view of the work of Sacconi (*Gazzetta*, 1949, 79, 141; *Nature*, 1949, 164, 70) who has shown that acids and salts lower H⁺ ion concentration of pure activated alumina. If pure alumina is held as a thick suspension in 0.1N-HCl the p_H is increased beyond 5.6, and with 0.2M-CuSO₄ and 0.2M-NiCl₂, the p_H of the former is changed from 3.45 and of the latter from 4.22 to a value as high as 5.8.

In the experiments described in this paper and the previous ones, the p_H of alumina was brought to 9.4 for cation adsorption by soaking it in water to which sufficient ammonia was added to give the required p_H value. In view of the discussion above, the p_H 9.4 for alumina has now been obtained by a buffer solution, so that depletion of H⁺ ions by cation adsorption may be balanced by the buffer. The buffer used for soaking alumina was made of 250 c.c. M/5-H₂BO₃ with 250 c.c. M/5-KCl + 185 c.c. M/5-NaOH, all made up to a litre. The data in column 3 of Table I for repetitions of these experiments under this condition, show the importance of buffering to correct p_H .

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